

Iododinitrobenzenes and their Derivatives

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1,2-Di-iodo-3,4- and 4,6-dinitro- and 1-iodo-3,4-dichloro-2,6-dinitro-benzenes have been prepared and also their derivatives by reaction with some nucleophilic agents.

In continuation of our previous work¹, nitration of 1,2-di-iodo-4-nitro- and 1-iodo-3,4-dichlorobenzenes has been studied. The nitration of 1,2-di-iodo-4-nitrobenzene² is expected to provide three dinitro isomers, viz., 3,4-(I), 4,5-(II), and 4,6-(III) dinitro-1,2-di-iodobenzenes. Only two isomers, (A) and (B), could be isolated from the reaction. The structure of (B) as 4,6-dinitro-1,2-di-iodobenzene(III) has been proved by its unequivocal synthesis from 2-iodo-4,6-dinitrophenylhydrazine³ by reacting it with iodine and also by its reaction with some nucleophilic agents, furnishing derivatives identical to those obtained from similar reaction with 1-chloro-2-iodo-4,6-dinitrobenzene⁴.

Compound (A) on reaction with *o*-aminophenol affords a phenoxazine containing only one iodine atom. This indicates that compound (A) is (I). Had it been (II), the phenoxazine formed would have been either free of iodine or would have possessed two iodine atoms, depending on whether the two -NO₂ groups or two iodine atoms had taken part in the condensation. The isolation of a phenoxazine containing only one iodine atom also indicates

1. Deorha and Mathur, *this Journal*, 1963, 40, 979.
2. Korner and Wender, *Gazzetta*, 1887, 17, 491.
3. Deorha and Sharma, *this Journal*, 1963, 40, 1047.
4. Sane and Joshi, *ibid.*, 1932, 9, 60; 1933, 10, 462.

that the site of nucleophilic attack in (I) is at position 3. This is supported by the fact that the phenylhydrazine obtained from (I) reacts with copper acetate in acetic acid to provide 1, 2-di-iodo-4-nitrobenzene². Had the site of nucleophilic attack been '4', the product of the reaction would have been 1,2-di-iodo-3-nitrobenzene.

The structure assigned to compound (A) is in agreement with its IR characteristics. Thus 1,2-di-iodo-4-nitrobenzene exhibits bands at 1515 cm^{-1} and 1351 cm^{-1} corresponding to the asymmetric and symmetric stretching valency vibrations of the $-\text{NO}_2$ group. Compound (A) containing two $-\text{NO}_2$ groups, however, exhibits multiple frequencies at 1534 cm^{-1} , 1515 cm^{-1} , 1368 cm^{-1} , and 1351 cm^{-1} . The multiple frequencies are due to two $-\text{NO}_2$ groups in a situation in which one at position 4 remains coplanar, whereas the other at position 3 is twisted out of the plane of the ring under the influence of steric effect of the bulky groups in both of its *ortho* positions. This reduces the degree of aromatic conjugation and new higher frequency bands at 1534 cm^{-1} and 1368 cm^{-1} occur.

The structure of the only product derived from dinitration of 3,4-dichloro-1-iodobenzene has been established as 3,4-dichloro-1-iodo-2,6-dinitrobenzene by (i) replacing one of the halogen atoms by a hydroxyl group⁵ when 3, 4-dichloro-2, 6-dinitrophenol⁶ is formed and (ii) replacing two halogen atoms by piperidino groups when a product, identical with the one similarly prepared from 1,3,4-trichloro-2,6-dinitrobenzene, i.e., 4-chloro-1,3-dipiperidino-2,6-dinitrobenzene⁷, is obtained.

EXPERIMENTAL

3,4-Dichloro-1-iodo-2,6-dinitrobenzene.—To a cooled suspension of 3,4-dichloro-1-iodobenzene⁷ (10 g.) in H_2SO_4 (42 ml, *d* 1.82) fuming nitric acid (28 ml, *d* 1.5) was added dropwise with shaking, the temperature being kept 10° . The mixture was then heated at about 110° for 10 hr., cooled, and poured on crushed ice. The solid mass was crystallised from ethanol to furnish 3,4-dichloro-1-iodo-2, 6-dinitrobenzene in yellow plates (7.2 g.), m.p. 128° . (Found: Cl, 19.32; I, 34.78. $\text{C}_6\text{H}_2\text{O}_4\text{N}_2\text{Cl}_2\text{I}$ requires Cl, 19.55; I, 34.98%).

Nitration of 1,2-di-iodo-4-nitrobenzene.—A mixture of 1,2-di-iodo-4-nitrobenzene⁸ (5 g.), H_2SO_4 (13 ml, *d* 1.82) and fuming nitric acid (3.5 ml, *d* 1.5) was heated on a boiling water bath for 4 hr. On cooling, the mixture was poured on crushed ice. The cream-coloured material separating was extracted with warm ethanol (3×20 ml). The ethanol-insoluble product (1.5 g.) on crystallisation from glacial acetic acid furnished 1,2-di-iodo-3,4-dinitrobenzene in pale yellow needles, m.p. 184° . (Found: I, 60.34. $\text{C}_6\text{H}_2\text{O}_4\text{N}_2\text{I}_2$ requires I, 60.47%).

The residue obtained by removing ethanol from the extract was dissolved in a boiling 1:1 mixture of CCl_4 and petroleum (b.p. $60\text{--}80^\circ$). On slight cooling, more of 1,2-di-iodo-3,4-dinitrobenzene (0.6g.) separated. On removing it immediately, the warm mother

5. Borsche, *Ber.*, 1917, 50, 1350.

6. Deorha *et al.*, *this Journal*, 1963, 40, 689.

7. Joshi and Gupta, *ibid.*, 1952, 29, 193.

8. Kraay, *Rec. trav. chim.*, 1930, 49, 1083.

liquor was allowed to cool. The crystalline solid separating was recrystallised eight times from CCl_4 and petroleum mixture to afford 1,2-di-iodo-4,6-dinitrobenzene (1.8 g.) in creamy crystals, m.p. 109° . (Found: I, 60.32. $\text{C}_6\text{H}_2\text{O}_4\text{N}_2\text{I}_2$ requires I, 60.47%).

The mother liquor on evaporation afforded an oil which could not be induced to crystallise.

1,2-Di-iodo-4,6-dinitrobenzene.—Iodine (1.5 g.) was gradually added to a suspension of 2-iodo-4,6-dinitrophenylhydrazine³ (1.5 g.) in boiling ethanol (20 ml). After refluxing the mixture for $\frac{1}{2}$ hr., it was diluted and excess of iodine removed with aqueous sodium sulphite. The solid after being washed well with water and dried was crystallised from 1:1 mixture of CCl_4 and petroleum (b.p. $60\text{--}80^\circ$) in yellow crystals, m.p. 110° . (Found: I, 60.19. $\text{C}_6\text{H}_2\text{O}_4\text{N}_2\text{I}_2$ requires I, 60.47%).

Reaction with Nucleophilic Agents.—The iododinitrobenzenes were allowed to react with ammonia and some amines by the procedure already reported⁴.

1,2-Di-iodo-4,6-dinitrobenzene furnished derivatives identical to those obtained from 1-chloro-2-iodo-4,6-dinitrobenzene⁴. The products obtained from 1,2-di-iodo-3,4-dinitrobenzene are recorded in Table I.

TABLE I

Reactant.	Derivative.	M.P.	Cryst. shape.	Formula.	% Iodine.	
					Found.	Reqd.
Ammonia	$\text{R}=\text{R}_1=\text{H}$	151°	Yellow flakes	$\text{C}_6\text{H}_4\text{O}_2\text{N}_2\text{I}_2$	64.60	65.11
Aniline	$\text{R}=\text{H}, \text{R}_1=\text{Ph}$	169°	Red plates	$\text{C}_{12}\text{H}_8\text{O}_2\text{N}_2\text{I}_2$	54.79	54.90
<i>o</i> -Toluidine	$\text{R}=\text{H}; \text{R}_1=\textit{o}\text{-Tol}$	134°	Reddish brown plates	$\text{C}_{13}\text{H}_{10}\text{O}_2\text{N}_2\text{I}_2$	53.08	52.91
<i>p</i> -Toluidine	$\text{R}=\text{H}; \text{R}_1=\textit{p}\text{-Tol}$	154°	Yellow needles	$\text{C}_{13}\text{H}_{10}\text{O}_2\text{N}_2\text{I}_2$	52.06	52.01
<i>p</i> -Anisidine	$\text{R}=\text{H}; \text{R}_1=\textit{p}\text{-MeOC}_6\text{H}_4$	171°	Red flakes	$\text{C}_{19}\text{H}_{16}\text{O}_4\text{N}_2\text{I}_2$	51.41	51.20
Dimethylamine	$\text{R}=\text{R}_1=\text{Me}$	144°	Orange-red flakes	$\text{C}_8\text{H}_{12}\text{O}_2\text{N}_2\text{I}_2$	60.76	60.74
Hydrazine hydrate	$\text{R}=\text{H}; \text{R}_1=\text{NH}_2^*$	202°	Orange-red	$\text{C}_6\text{H}_5\text{O}_2\text{N}_3\text{I}$	62.73	62.71

*The hydrazones of benzaldehyde and acetone, prepared in the usual way, have the following characteristics respectively: m.p. 251° , red (Found: I, 51.81. $\text{C}_{13}\text{H}_9\text{O}_2\text{N}_2\text{I}_2$ requires I, 51.52%); m.p. 113° , dull orange (Found: I, 56.97. $\text{C}_9\text{H}_9\text{O}_2\text{N}_2\text{I}_2$ requires I, 57.07%).

5-Iodo-2-nitrophenoxazine.—A mixture of product (A) (0.5 g.), *o*-aminophenol (0.15 g.), and anhydrous sodium acetate (0.6 g.) in anhydrous ethanol (12 ml) was refluxed for 6 hr. The mass was cooled, filtered, and washed successively with water, HCl (dil.), and ethanol. The crude product was crystallised from ethanol in reddish brown crystals, m.p. 181° . (Found: I, 35.75. $\text{C}_{12}\text{H}_7\text{O}_3\text{N}_2\text{I}$ requires I, 35.87%).

4-Chloro-1,3-dipiperidino-2,6-dinitrobenzene.—A mixture of 3,4-dichloro-1-iodo-2,6-dinitrobenzene (0.9 g.), piperidine (1 ml) and anhydrous sodium acetate (1 g.) in ethanol (10 ml) was refluxed on a water bath for 2 hr. The product separating was crystallised from acetic acid in shining yellow needles, m.p. 145°.

An identical product⁷ was formed if an equivalent amount of 1,3,4-trichloro-2,6-dinitrobenzene be used in place of the preceding iododichlorodinitrobenzene.

3,4-Dichloro-2,6-dinitrophenol.—After heating the dinitro compound (0.5 g.), derived from 3,4-dichloro-1-iodobenzene, with acetamide (4 g.) and sodium acetate (2 g.) for 1 hr., the melt was dissolved in a strong ammonium hydroxide solution (20 ml). The solution was heated with activated charcoal on a water bath for 2 hr. Acidification of the filtrate afforded the dichlorodinitrophenol which was crystallised from ethanol in yellow crystals, m.p. 168°, undepressed on admixture with 3,4-dichloro-2,6-dinitrophenol obtained from dinitration of 3,4-dichlorophenol. (Found: Cl, 27.82. Calc. for $C_6H_2O_2N_2Cl_2$: Cl, 28.06%).

Its acetyl derivative separated from ethanol in yellow crystals, m.p. 128° (lit.⁶ m.p. 128°).

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